

Concepts for metadata interoperability, harmonization and technical integration of
PID infrastructure

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Deliverable 2.3 & 2.4

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20 December 2024

Imprint

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Date of publication	20 December 2024
Version	Version 1.0
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14506138
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Deliverable	2.3 & 2.4

About

PID4NFDI (<https://base4nfdi.de/projects/pid4nfdi>) is the basic service for persistent identifiers in development for the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). PID4NFDI is part of and funded through Base4NFDI.

Funded by DFG as part of NFDI. DFG Grant Number: 521466146

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Background

This report presents a conceptual framework developed by the PID4NFDI to advance metadata interoperability, harmonization, and technical integration of Persistent Identifier (PID) infrastructures in the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). Building upon the groundwork laid during the initialization phase¹ and guided by the vision outlined in the integration phase proposal². Our approach integrates insights from community surveys, interviews with use case partners, and extensive engagement with NFDI consortia members.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281250>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281255>

Concept for Metadata Interoperability and Harmonization (D2.4)

Metadata interoperability is fundamental for the effective exchange and reuse of research data within NFDI and its community. Achieving metadata interoperability will enable seamless data integration, foster cross-disciplinary research, and enhance the global visibility of NFDI research outputs.

The current landscape features a variety of metadata standards, vocabularies, and schemas designed to meet the specific needs of different disciplines. While this diversity is valuable, it also creates fragmentation, leading to increased administrative burdens, reduced findability, and challenges in data sharing and reuse.

This report presents a comprehensive strategy developed by PID4NFDI to address these challenges while advancing the FAIR principles. It incorporates insights from a recent survey³, contributions from use case partners (e.g., qualitative interviews), and extensive engagement with NFDI consortia members.

PID4NFDI is a collaborative initiative led by DataCite, the Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung Göttingen (GWDG), the Helmholtz Open Science Office, and the Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB) – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology.

The consortium works closely with experienced PID infrastructure users to leverage their insights and amplify the impact of PID adoption within NFDI workflows⁴.

Primary Goal

The primary goal is the creation of a sustainable, scalable, and community-driven framework for metadata interoperability that reduces administrative burden, enhances metadata quality, and improves research data discoverability. This strategy seeks to harmonize metadata practices across the NFDI community, fostering compliance with the FAIR principles and supporting the development of a unified metadata ecosystem.

³ El-Gebali, S., Hagemann-Wilholt, S., Böhm, J., & Kahlert, T. (2024). D1.1 Landscape of PID practices within NFDI services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14277479>

⁴ <http://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/>

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Concepts

Aligning Metadata Standards

Focus: Align metadata standards across the NFDI community, prioritize alignment of—and with—widely used schemas and standards (e.g., DataCite Metadata Schema, Schema.org, Bioschemas, maDMP, DCAT, and PID Kernel Profiles).

Actions:

- Promote the use of recognized metadata standards to reduce fragmentation and improve interoperability.
- Facilitate mapping of PID-service-provider metadata requirements to discipline-specific schemas.
- Adopt controlled vocabularies to ensure metadata consistency.
- Collaborate with stakeholders, including schema developers and domain-specific groups, to address real-world challenges.

Centralizing Schema Management

Focus: Centralize schema management to reduce redundancies, ensure interoperability, and enable effective metadata integration.

Actions:

- Engage with key frameworks like the EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) and the Data Type Registry (DTR) from FAIRCORE4EOSC.
- Encourage community contributions to registries like MSCR and DTR.
- Promote accessibility and discoverability of schemas, crosswalks, and mappings.

Promoting Metadata Granularity

Focus: Enhance metadata granularity to capture nuanced information, meeting the diverse needs of research disciplines.

Actions:

- Support detailed metadata descriptions, including sub-unit descriptions.
- Ensure cohesion across disciplines by using common standards as a base layer and extending them with community-driven vocabularies.
- Provide best practice guidelines for implementing metadata granularity.

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Developing Tools for Metadata Assessment

Focus: Improve metadata quality through effective tools and practices for assessment and monitoring.

Actions:

- Prototype tools for assessing and monitoring metadata quality.
- Generate actionable reports on metadata completeness and adherence to FAIR principles.
- Establish a Metadata Consultation Framework for ongoing support.
- Promote metadata health awareness through outreach initiatives.

Facilitating Interoperability Through Early PID Integration

Focus: Integrate PIDs into workflows early in the research lifecycle to enhance metadata interoperability and consistency.

Actions:

- Collaborate with research workflow stakeholders to embed PIDs in tools like Data Management Plans (DMPs) and Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs).
- Expand PID use to include diverse resource types, promoting cross-disciplinary collaboration.
- Enable interlinked metadata through related identifiers.
- Encourage standard adoption and integrate PID-related standards into workflow software.

Strengthening Training and Capacity Building

Focus: Build community expertise to ensure effective adoption and use of metadata standards and practices⁵.

Actions:

- Offer standardized training resources focused on metadata quality and standards alignment.
- Host workshops and events to engage stakeholders and provide hands-on learning opportunities.

⁵ For details on training opportunities to improve PID management: Kahlert, T., & Hagemann-Wilholt, S. (2024). D3.2 PID4NFDI Training Concept. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14267399>

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- Develop certification programs to recognize expertise and encourage participation.

Leveraging the PID Coordination Hub

Focus: Utilize the PID Coordination Hub as a central resource for fostering collaboration, disseminating best practices, and scaling successful initiatives.

Actions:

- Facilitate cross-consortium collaboration through the Hub.
- Share lessons learned and build a repository of practical guidance for metadata management.
- Scale successful practices and promote standardized frameworks through the Hub.

Task Breakdown

Below, each task (T2.1 to T2.6) is outlined with suggested actions to align with the overarching concepts and goals, keeping in mind flexibility and adaptability.

T2.1 Metadata quality assessment and gap analysis (Lead: DataCite)

Milestone: M2.1 Analysis of metadata and standards according to selected use cases (T2.1)

Aim: Evaluate current metadata approaches within NFDI and identify areas for improved alignment with PID provider standards (e.g., DataCite). This includes reviewing selected schemas, and exploring opportunities for enhanced PID integration.

Potential Activities:

- T2.1.1: Review selected metadata schemas and standards in use.
- T2.1.2: Identify gaps where PID requirements are not fully addressed.
- T2.1.3: Outline areas for enhanced integration with ELNs and DMPs.

Deliverable: A report detailing observed practices, identifying gaps relative to the DataCite Schema, and offering initial suggestions for future improvements.

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T2.2 Develop best practices and guidelines (Lead: DataCite)

Aim: Use insights from T2.1 to develop concrete examples, guidelines, and checklists to improve metadata quality.

Potential Activities:

- T2.2.1: Provide human-readable examples documenting best practices for metadata quality.
- T2.2.2: Highlight the importance of linking research outputs through related identifiers, fostering richer metadata networks.
- T2.2.3: Explore granular sub-unit descriptions, discipline-specific metadata integration, and the use of community-driven vocabularies and mappings.
- T2.2.4: Pilot a Metadata Completeness Checklist for repositories.
- T2.2.5: Create guidelines for metadata practices, ensuring alignment with project goals and collaboration with WP4 and WP5.

Deliverable: Best practice guides, feedback reports, and a Metadata Completeness Checklist, made available through the PID Coordination Hub to support community adoption.

T2.3 Tools for metadata assessment and monitoring (Lead: DataCite)

Milestone: M2.2 Technical feasibility assessment for metadata monitoring tools

Aim: Explore the feasibility of monitoring tools (e.g., dashboards) to track metadata quality, completeness, and consistency. Examine how these tools might connect with existing services and how to support users in applying them.

Potential Activities:

- T2.3.1: Identify key functionalities and metadata elements required for assessment and monitoring.
- T2.3.2: Prototype dashboards to visualize metadata completeness and quality, providing pilot reports to selected use cases.
- T2.3.3: Assess the feasibility of integrating real-time data feeds for up-to-date insights.
- T2.3.4: Compare dashboard requirements with FAIR Checker tools to ensure adherence to FAIR principles.
- T2.3.5: Support WP4 and WP5 in training and promoting Metadata Health Awareness.

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- T2.3.6: Design a Metadata Consultation Framework to offer dedicated support.
- T2.3.7: Collaborate with the Search and Harvesting working group within the (Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance section to enhance tool functionalities.

Deliverable: A prototype framework, technical feasibility reports, metadata quality assessment reports, comparisons to FAIR principles, and training/outreach materials.

T2.4 Promote integration and interoperability (Lead: DataCite, GWDG)

Milestone: M2.3 Feedback and verification of interoperability among selected use cases (T2.4)

Aim: Align PID services with broader frameworks, such as FDOs and EOSC, to improve interoperability. Explore strategies for metadata enhancements within existing systems and broader initiatives.

Potential Activities:

- T2.4.1: Aligning PID service provider requirements to FDO profiles.
- T2.4.2: Examine integration strategies, including technical examples of PID integrations in tools like ELNs and DMPs (e.g., plugins in custom-built platforms).
- T2.4.3: Collaborate with FAIRCORE4EOSC to incorporate Data Typing as a service into the PID Coordination Hub.
- T2.4.4: Promote the use of shared frameworks, schemas, and standards via the PID Coordination Hub.
- T2.4.5: Encourage interoperability solutions such as APIs and consistent identifiers across disciplines.
- T2.4.6: Foster NFDI participation in and engaging with key frameworks like the EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR), contributing to tools that expose and standardize NFDI metadata crosswalking and data typing practices.

Deliverable: A conceptual integration strategy, training materials on API usage, and technical examples of PID registrations in ELNs and DMPs.

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T2.5 Specific focus on material samples and research instruments: monitoring and guidance (Lead: DataCite, TIB)

Milestone: M2.4 Increased collaboration among consortia and disciplines, and increased rate of PID registrations for samples and instruments.

Aim: Promote early-stage registration of PIDs for material samples and instruments within workflows like DMPs and ELNs, while exploring their integration into SKGs and providing training and outreach.

Potential Activities:

- T2.5.1: Provide human-readable examples of PID registration for selected resource types.
- T2.5.2: Collaborate with WP4 and WP5 on training efforts promoting best practices.
- T2.5.3: Identify use cases demonstrating effective PID registration workflows (e.g. integration into DMPs and ELNs).
- T2.5.4: Support IGSN ID registrations for interested use cases.
- T2.5.5: Advise schema developers and domain experts in Base Services (TS4NFDI, KGI4NFDI, DMP4NFDI) on integrating selected resource types into SKGs.
- T2.5.6: Monitor the adoption and usage of PIDs for specific resource types.

Deliverable: Examples of best practices, enriched PID metadata for samples and instruments, and reports on adoption and usage metrics.

T2.6 Explore metadata requirements for projects and facility usage awards (Lead: DataCite, TIB)

Milestone: M2.5 Facilitation of accelerated adoption of PIDs for projects and facility usage awards.

Aim: Explore the use of Project and Award PIDs to track funding outcomes and resource reuse, focusing on their integration into DMPs, ELNs, and SKGs.

Potential Activities:

- T2.6.1: Analyze existing metadata practices for Project and Facility usage PIDs highlighting challenges and opportunities.
- T2.6.2: Promote early registration of projects, awards, and facilities within research processes.

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- T2.6.5: Collaborate with KGI4NFDI to explore methodologies for integrating Project IDs and Grant IDs in SKGs.
- T2.6.6: Develop full human-readable examples for selected resource types.
- T2.6.7: Support training and outreach activities with WP4 and WP5 on the usage of Project IDs and Grant IDs.
- T2.6.9: Monitor the adoption and usage of Project IDs and Grant IDs.

Deliverable: Training materials and recommendations detailing metadata requirements, current practices, and examples of PID integrations.

Concept for technical integration of PID infrastructure (D2.3)

T3.1 PIDs for research instruments: Advancing the infrastructure (Lead: TIB)

Aim: Facilitate the discovery and registration of PIDs for research instruments by establishing a unified framework that integrates data from various providers, enhances community support, and links instruments with related research outputs.

Develop Unified Framework for Instrument PIDs

- T3.1.1: Design and implement a unified framework that integrates data from multiple PID providers for research instruments.
- T3.1.2: Establish B2INST as a low-barrier service, providing enhanced community support and metadata extensions specifically for research instrument registration.

Crosslinking Instruments with Research Outputs

- T3.1.3: Develop mechanisms to crosslink instrument PIDs with related research outputs, including:
 - Datasets with measurement data by instruments
 - Literature citing used instruments
 - Individuals and organizations operating instruments
 - Instrument calibrations

Best Practices Development and Collaboration

- T3.1.4: Collaborate with PID providers to develop and publish best practices for linking instrument PIDs with related PIDs, enhancing metadata networks (referencing T2.5).
- T3.1.5: Document and disseminate best practices through the PID Coordination Hub and relevant training materials.

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Implement Sensor Management System Use Case

- T3.1.6: Integrate the Sensor Management System developed for the Earth system science community (notably NFDI4Earth) as a key use case for instrument identifiers.
- T3.1.7: Monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the Sensor Management System integration, gathering feedback for continuous improvement.

Deliverable: Comprehensive framework for research instrument PIDs, established B2INST service with community support, crosslinked instrument PIDs with research outputs, documented best practices, and a case study report on the Sensor Management System integration.

T3.2 Prefix registration service (Lead: GWDG)

Aim: Promote rapid PID adoption by implementing a simple prefix registration service that offers free PID services for select use cases during the project and establishes the foundation for sustained PID generation post-project.

Implement Prefix Registration System

- T3.2.1: Design and deploy a prefix registration service for use case partners.
- T3.2.2: Offer free PID services for approximately 10 use cases during the project duration to encourage adoption.

Manage Test Prefixes

- T3.2.3: Allocate and distribute test prefixes for technical integration and testing purposes, ensuring they are available in larger quantities, but without persistence guarantees.
- T3.2.4: Monitor the usage of test prefixes and gather feedback to inform future improvements.

Establish Sustainability for PID Generation

- T3.2.5: Develop and negotiate dedicated contracts with ePIC service providers to ensure continued PID generation after the project concludes.
- T3.2.6: Explore and document potential funding models or partnerships to support the long-term sustainability of the prefix registration service.

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Deliverable: Operational prefix registration service, distribution and management of test prefixes, sustainability plan for ongoing PID generation, and documentation of contracts with ePIC service providers.

T3.3 Technical integration of the services (Lead: GWDG)

Aim: Integrate key technical services, including the Data Type Registry (DTR), Prefix Registration Service, and PID Management Repository (PIDMR), into the Coordination Hub. Ensure secure registration processes and customized user interfaces tailored to NFDI-specific requirements.

Integrate Technical Services

- T3.3.1: Seamlessly integrate with EOSC components such as the Data Type Registry (DTR), Prefix Registration Service, and PID Metaresolver (PIDMR) into the PID Coordination Hub.
- T3.3.2: Ensure interoperability between these services to facilitate smooth PID registration and management workflows.

Implement Authentication and Authorization

- T3.3.3: Integrate authentication mechanisms required for registering new types and PID service providers through the NFDI Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) developed by IAM4NFDI to facilitate accessibility of the services.
- T3.3.4: Ensure secure access controls are in place to protect sensitive PID registration data.

Customize User Interface

- T3.3.5: Develop and customize the user interface of the Coordination Hub to meet NFDI-specific requirements, ensuring it is user-friendly and accessible.
- T3.3.6: Conduct user testing sessions to gather feedback on the interface design and make necessary adjustments for optimal usability.

Facilitate Registration of Types and Profiles

- T3.3.7: Utilize the DTR to facilitate the registration of data types and profiles, enabling community-specific metadata schemata.

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- T3.3.8: Implement validation mechanisms within the DTR to ensure metadata compliance against registered profiles, enhancing overall metadata quality.

Documentation and Training

- T3.3.9: Develop comprehensive technical documentation outlining the integration process, user guides for the services, and best practices for using the integrated services.
- T3.3.10: Conduct training sessions and workshops for NFDI service providers and infrastructure managers on utilizing the integrated services effectively.

Deliverable: Fully integrated technical services within the Coordination Hub, secure authentication and authorization mechanisms, customized and user-tested interface, comprehensive technical documentation, and completed training sessions for stakeholders.